

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING LANGUAGE

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Abstract. In this research paper it is explained the integration of the artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of the languages. You can find the answer to the questions: How will it affect the way we hire and prepare our teachers? Will technology eventually take the role of teachers?

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, pronunciation, writing skills, reading comprehension, pedagogical approaches.

Introduction. The concept of artificial intelligence has captivated global attention, resulting in numerous media coverage and stimulating intense discussions. Those in the education field are having lively arguments about how AI will affect our students' ability to learn and grow. How will it affect the way we hire and prepare our teachers? Will technology eventually take the role of teachers? In particular, there are several chances to include AI-powered technology in language instruction. We have seen some successful apps built employing AI to construct adaptive learning paths for language learners, even before the emergence of generative AI tools like ChatGPT. Generative AI techniques provide significant possibilities for language practice. Realizing potential involves motivation and skills from students, instructors, and other stakeholders. It is obvious that there are dangers and obstacles that need to be investigated, and it is important to pay attention to and thoroughly evaluate the opinions of the people these technologies are intended for. This publication aims to accomplish just that. The article acknowledges the impact of AI on English language teaching and aims to comprehend the changes that are occurring.

Main part. The researched data highlighted five important areas where AI is being applied in ELT, including developing speaking, writing, and reading abilities, as well as supporting pedagogical practices. AI-powered tools and programs are available to help learners improve their pronunciation, which has been identified as an important sub-skill in research on the application of AI in speech. In a 2016 study with Taiwanese learners, Liu and Hung discovered that using AI and a spectrogram to visualize pitch enhanced speech by eliminating flatness and intonation patterns. The use of AI in writing is primarily connected to grammar and vocabulary learning. Lo (2023) discovered, for instance, that having access to neural machines Learners' vocabulary improved as a result of translation programs, particularly when clear or specialized expressions were used. The usage of AI

grammar checkers in writing is another popular application of AI. For example, students who used the AI-powered tool Grammarly made fewer grammatical errors and wrote with more lexical variation than students who did not, according to a study conducted in higher education by Dizon and Gayed (2021). Among the pedagogical approaches to AI use for writing skills, only one emerged: supporting feedback-giving. Research on writing pedagogy have frequently been linked to artificial intelligence (AI) tools that offer feedback through grammar and spelling checkers, similar to the Grammarly study conducted by Dizon and Gayed in 2021 (see above). The application of Grammarly as a feedback tool for English language learners was also investigated by Nazari et al. (2021). They noted improvements in behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement in addition to an increase in writing self-efficacy. A range of artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as grammar checkers, writing assistants, translation tools, and pattern checkers, were utilized to support writing abilities. Despite the fact that some research did use AI to improve the receptive skill of Reading was far less common than speaking and writing, which are productive skills. The only component of improving reading comprehension that seemed to require special attention was vocabulary development; no particular application of gaming to bolster pedagogy was identified. For example, Zheng et al. (2015) investigated how vocabulary is learned for reading in the context of English-language gaming quest-play in the video game World of Warcraft (WoW). The results imply that, by contextualizing frequently decontextualized vocabulary, learners have opportunities to learn vocabulary and understand meaning via games beyond what can be provided by a textbook or classroom. This is a reference to the approaches, plans, and procedures employed in ELT facilitation. It is noteworthy that many traditional pedagogical approaches, like lectures and explanations, are still used in classrooms despite the quick changes in technology available. Several studies looked at various strategies that seem to offer a more customized learning experience. For instance, Kim (2022) investigated how Korean students preparing for the Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC) were affected by pedagogical strategies such as score predictions, lectures, explanations, and practice exams. After completing a diagnostic assessment, learners received lectures, explanations, and practice exams tailored to their learning level by the AI.

Conclusion. The publication gives us to understand the relationship between artificial intelligence and teaching English, as well as how educators are utilizing new technologies. It also poses important questions for additional thought and identifies crucial next steps that will support its safe integration into our teaching methods.

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